

Online Supplement: Leading Through the Fire and Beyond: A Competency Model for Platoon Leaders in Fire Services

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1) Interview guideline of Study 1

1. Introduction to the Interview

- **Greeting and Introduction:** Welcome the participant and thank them for their participation.
- **Objective of the Interview:** Explain that the goal of the interview is to gain insight into the professional field and leadership work of platoon leaders and the relevant competences.
- **Duration of the Interview:** Inform the participant that the interview will last approximately 30 to 60 minutes.
- **Data Protection:** Obtain consent for the use of the collected data in accordance with GDPR and for the audio recording, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity of the interview.
- **Honest Answers:** Request honest and unfiltered answers, emphasizing that the focus is on identifying relevant competences rather than evaluating performance.
- **Clarification of Open Questions:** Address any open questions.

2. Collection of Personal Information

- **Demographic Data:** Ask for age, gender, and highest educational qualification.
- **Duration of Fire Department Affiliation and Leadership Experience:** Inquire about the duration of affiliation with the fire department and the duration of leadership experience.
- **Platoon Leader Training:** Ask about the timing and duration of platoon leader training and how long the participant has been in the platoon leader role.
- **Fire Department Unit:** Determine whether the participant is part of a career fire department or a volunteer fire department.

3. Collection of Critical Leadership Situations

A. Description of Positive Leadership Situations in Operations

- **Recall a Positive Situation:** Ask the participant to recall a critical operational situation where they, as a platoon leader, reacted and acted particularly well and successfully resolved the situation.

- **Detailed Description:** Request a detailed description of the chosen situation.
- **Follow-up Questions:**
 - How and why did you react in this way?
 - Why didn't you react differently?
 - What was the timeline?
 - What were you thinking and feeling?
 - How did the situation arise?
 - How did your behavior affect the outcome?
 - What were the consequences of the situation?
- **Success Criteria:** Ask why they believe this leadership situation was successful and how they measure success.
- **Importance and Frequency:** Have them rate the importance and frequency of such situations on a 5-point scale.
- **Additional Situations:** Ask if they can recall another situation where they reacted particularly well.

B. Description of Negative Leadership Situations in Operations

- **Recall a Negative Situation:** Ask the participant to recall a critical operational situation where they, as a platoon leader, did not react and act as well and could not resolve the situation successfully.
- **Detailed Description:** Request a detailed description of the chosen situation.
- **Follow-up Questions:**
 - How and why did you react in this way?
 - Why didn't you react differently?
 - What was the timeline?
 - What were you thinking and feeling?
 - How did the situation arise?
 - How did your behavior affect the outcome?
 - What were the consequences of the situation?
- **Failure Criteria:** Ask why they believe this leadership situation was less successful and how they measure failure.

- **Importance and Frequency:** Have them rate the importance and frequency of such situations on a 5-point scale.
- **Additional Situations:** Ask if they can recall another situation where they did not react as well.

C. Description of Positive Leadership Situations Outside of Operations

- **Additional Responsibilities:** Ask if they have additional responsibilities outside of operations, such as being a platoon leader.
- **Recall a Positive Situation:** Ask the participant to recall a critical situation outside of operations where they, as a platoon leader, reacted and acted particularly well and successfully resolved the situation.
- **Detailed Description:** Request a detailed description of the chosen situation.
- **Follow-up Questions:**
 - How and why did you react in this way?
 - Why didn't you react differently?
 - What was the timeline?
 - What were you thinking and feeling?
 - How did the situation arise?
 - How did your behavior affect the outcome?
 - What were the consequences of the situation?
- **Success Criteria:** Ask why they believe this leadership situation was successful and how they measure success.
- **Importance and Frequency:** Have them rate the importance and frequency of such situations on a 5-point scale.
- **Additional Situations:** Ask if they can recall another situation where they reacted particularly well.

D. Description of Negative Leadership Situations Outside of Operations

- **Recall a Negative Situation:** Ask the participant to recall a critical situation outside of operations where they, as a platoon leader, did not react and act as well and could not resolve the situation successfully.
- **Detailed Description:** Request a detailed description of the chosen situation.
- **Follow-up Questions:**
 - How and why did you react in this way?

- Why didn't you react differently?
- What was the timeline?
- What were you thinking and feeling?
- How did the situation arise?
- How did your behavior affect the outcome?
- What were the consequences of the situation?
- **Failure Criteria:** Ask why they believe this leadership situation was less successful and how they measure failure.
- **Importance and Frequency:** Have them rate the importance and frequency of such situations on a 5-point scale.
- **Additional Situations:** Ask if they can recall another situation where they did not react as well.

4. Direct Inquiry of Relevant Competences

- **List Competences:** Ask the participant to list the competences that are particularly relevant for them as a platoon leader in their daily work, distinguishing between competences for operations and those for activities outside of operations.

5. Conclusion of the Interview

- **Clarification of Open Questions:** Address any open questions.
- **Interest in Study Results:** Ask if they are interested in receiving the study results and, if so, request their email address to send the results.
- **Thank You and Farewell:** Thank the participant for their participation and bid them farewell.

2) Table 1: Criteria used by interviewees to assess success

In the table below, the criteria that were used by the participants to evaluate situations as successful (positive, result of effective work behavior) or unsuccessful (negative, result of ineffective work behavior) are summarized. These criteria underscore the importance of the competences as they directly reflect the impact that high or low levels of the extracted competences in platoon leaders can have.

Overview of criteria for success or failure in leadership situations mentioned by participants

Situation type	Criteria for success	Criteria for failure
Action phases	<u>Operational result</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Achieving an operational goal - Preventing large-scale damage - Receiving positive feedback on operational result 	<u>Operational result</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preventable, non-satisfactory operational results - Unpreventable, non-satisfactory operational results
	<u>Operational process</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applying an effective operational strategy - High level of safety for the team during operations - Effective leadership shown by platoon leader - Calmness, structure, and goal orientation during operation - Effective cooperation of the team with other involved parties - Effective cooperation with other fire services - Giving positive feedback on operational process 	<u>Operational process</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preventable time loss - Unnecessarily putting the team in danger - Ineffective, erroneous communication during operation - Incorrect performance of tasks by the platoon leader, resulting in a lack of leadership at the operational scene - Disregard of operational rules by the team - Disobedience of the crew to the platoon leader and undermining his leadership authority

Interim phases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhancing the team's motivation - Enhancing harmony, fellowship, cohesion, and respect within the team - Enhancing professionalism, readiness, and skills of the team - Improving the reputation of the fire department among the population - Organizing and designing activities during interim phases - Fulfillment of the platoon leader's duty of care for the team 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Team undermining platoon leaders' function - Resignation of a member from the fire department for avoidable reasons - Prevention of a solution to relevant factual problems - Emergence of frustration in the team - Reduction of motivation, engagement, and loyalty in the team - Emergence of conflict in the team; decreasing harmony - Unsuccessful communication between leaders and members
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Note. Mentioned criteria were aggregated into overarching categories. N = 25.

3) Initial list of competencies (Study 1)

Professional Competency

- Availability and Applicability of Expertise
- Awareness of Dangers

Methodological Competency

- Leadership Presence
- Situational Overview and Control
- Development and Adherence to a Work Structure
- Quick Evaluation and Decision-Making
- Re-evaluation of Each Situation
- Reflection and Flexibility in Approach
- Conscious Selective Perception
- Anticipating Events and Actions
- Improvisation
- Exploration and Understanding of Causal Relationships
- Creativity in Approach

Social Competency

- Calm Issuance of Clear Commands
- Factual and Respectful Communication
- Support Readiness for the Team
- Individual Deployment and Promotion of the Team
- Trustful, Engaged Collaboration
- Task Delegation and Coordination
- Team Leadership and Support
- Promoting Team Cohesion
- Encouraging Individual Strengths
- Public Relations Work
- Empathy
- Fairness and Equality

Self-Competency

- Maintaining Inner/Outer Calmness
- Reflection and Processing of Experiences
- Self-Efficacy
- Overcoming Failures
- Loyalty and Integrity
- Resilience and Stress Tolerance
- Initiative
- Organization and Planning Skills
- Role Awareness
- Personal Motivation for Further Development

4) Final competency definitions (Study 2)

Professional competency

Firefighting expertise

Platoon leaders have extensive specialist knowledge to successfully fulfill their tasks. This specialist knowledge is called upon and applied in various situations inside and outside of operations. They have a keen awareness of real and potential dangers. Dangers to persons, e.g. to the crew, are quickly and reliably recognized, correctly assessed and consistently taken into account in further action.

Methodological competency

Analytical competence

Platoon leaders quickly grasp essential information and build up a comprehensive understanding of situations inside and outside the operation. They think about every problem anew and do not rely solely on their experience and familiar patterns. They understand complex interrelationships and work with great perseverance to uncover them.

Decision-making

Platoon leaders can make decisions quickly, particularly regarding prioritization and procedures in operations, but also in their day-to-day work. They record and evaluate all possible courses of action, including standard procedures and other creative solutions, against the background of the situation's requirements.

Structuring

Platoon leaders develop a structured approach based on relevant information, their own knowledge and experience and formulate specific, achievable goals. They divide the measures to be carried out into meaningful subtasks. They delegate these to available units or employees and ensure coordination between those involved. They work through their formulated tactics in a targeted, consistent and conscientious manner.

Adaptation and Control

Platoon leaders continuously evaluate situations in the operation and at the watch and reflect on their actions. If previous measures do not produce a satisfactory result, circumstances change or new information arises, they adapt their approach accordingly. They take the necessary measures to be able to control situations effectively. They think ahead in their actions and openly always weigh up subsequent steps.

Improvisation

Platoon leaders improvise quickly and effectively when the situation requires it, especially when standard procedures are not possible, personnel or technical equipment are lacking, or the behavior of the crew or employees does not meet the expectations of the platoon leaders. To achieve their set goals, they think beyond established procedures and develop new creative measures appropriate to the situation.

Planning and Organizing

Platoon leaders plan and organize the work in their area of responsibility effectively and with foresight. They recognize and consider relevant structural and personal resources and assume responsibility for ensuring service capability. They carry out events and other activities within the fire department in a coordinated manner on given occasions.

Optimizing processes

Platoon leaders recognize long-term work needs as well as potential for improvement and generate ideas for measures to address them. They are motivated to continuously develop the fire department and are willing to invest time and energy to achieve this goal.

Social competency

Assertiveness

If necessary, platoon leaders use their authority to assert their ideas, opinions and goals in the face of resistance. If the situation allows, they actively engage in exchange.

Conflict competence

Platoon leaders resolve their own conflicts and those within the team respectfully and constructively. They use tact in conflict situations and act objectively and neutrally. They actively contribute to harmony within the team.

Communication

Platoon leaders communicate effectively by using their words, facial expressions and gestures skillfully and appropriately for the situation. Their communication is characterized by calmness, clarity and objectivity, while they present their information in an understandable way. At the same time, they show sensitivity by taking in their conversation partner's statements objectively, listening actively and processing them precisely and quickly. If anything is unclear, they ask specific questions. It is crucial that platoon leaders can give orders clearly and without contradiction. During operations, the platoon leader's orders should contain all the necessary information and be appropriate to the situation, regardless of whether the command is cooperative or authoritarian. The way in which orders are given should not confuse the crew but should always have a motivating effect.

Team cooperation

Platoon leaders cooperate effectively with other people from the fire services and other relevant organizations. In doing so, they identify common goals and ensure comradely, collegial and professional coordination. Cooperation between platoon leaders takes place on an equal footing, is based on trust and involves the transparent sharing of information. In addition, platoon leaders generally make their decisions together with the relevant cooperation partners.

Public sensitivity

Platoon leaders continuously consider the impact of their actions and the fire department in general on the civilians involved and the public. They present the fire department in a positive light.

Empathy

Platoon leaders put themselves in other people's shoes to understand their motives, feelings and actions. If the situation requires it, they act empathetically, listen actively and respond to the other person. They show particular sensitivity when in contact with victims and their relatives.

Team sensitivity and care

Platoon leaders perceive the feelings, moods and current concerns of the team and respond individually to the team's needs. At the same time, they must assess how much freedom the team needs and whether active intervention is required. They ensure the safety of the team and see this as an essential criterion for their actions and

procedures. They promote the processing of negative or traumatic operational experiences and ensure the operational readiness of the crew through adequate basic and advanced training. Platoon leaders should also deal with the personal problems of the crew in a professional manner and actively support them by listening and giving advice. This contributes to a positive team atmosphere, whereby it is crucial to build up, recognize and praise the team with positive input. The fair and equitable treatment of all team members is fundamental to this.

Development

Platoon leaders know the level of training, skills and personality of their team members in order to deploy them optimally. They recognize the need to intervene themselves in relevant situations by knowing the level of development of their team members. They support their team by continuously challenging them professionally and at the same time rely on calm explanations, corrections and constructive feedback. Platoon leaders support the exchange of opinions and feedback process within the team at all levels. They give constructive feedback themselves, request it from the team and deal with it intensively. In this way, they raise awareness of individual strengths and weaknesses within the team.

Self-competency

Willingness and ability to learn

Platoon leaders are motivated to continuously develop personally and to expand their own knowledge and build up new competencies. They also show openness and interest in non-fire service-specific topics such as communication or leadership.

Role clarity and integrity

Platoon leaders consciously position themselves in their role as managers, make their leadership claim clear and actively take on leadership tasks. They act confidently and self-assuredly towards the crew and other relevant stakeholders. They take responsibility, act as role models and act loyally and with integrity in the interests of their team and the fire department. Platoon leaders stand up for their team without primarily pursuing their own interests. They treat everyone with respect and as equals. In operational situations, platoon leaders lead their team at close range without being directly involved in the action.

Resilience

Platoon leaders must be able to deal with great uncertainty and chaos and work in a concentrated and focused manner in overwhelming situations within and outside of operations. They possess coping strategies to deal with the strains of their role and thus maintain their operational readiness and health.

Reflection competence

Platoon leaders continuously reflect on themselves and situations they have experienced and develop an understanding of their abilities, strengths and weaknesses as well as their impact on others. They deepen this understanding through the ongoing analysis of their behavior and the reactions of those around them, as well as through the ongoing revision of learned patterns and rules. They recognize their own vulnerability and seek support when needed. They are aware of their current emotional, psychological and physical state and take this into account in their actions. They maintain their motivation and positive attitude towards the team and the fire department in general, even in the face of failures and setbacks. They develop ways of dealing with frustration.

Self-regulation

Platoon leaders maintain inner calm in stressful and hectic situations and show this to the outside world in order to radiate order, calm and stability to the team and everyone involved at all times. In these stressful situations, platoon leaders must always pay attention to the emotionality and sharpness that quickly arises in their communication, take it out and have an orienting and calming effect.

5) Table 2: Standard deviations of importance ratings (Study 2)

Competence	Mean within action phases	SD within Action phases	Mean between action phases	SD between Action phases
Firefighting expertise	5.64	0.72	4.83	0.89
Analytical competence	5.40	0.73	4.81	0.83
Decision-making	5.73	0.55	4.79	0.85
Planning and organizing	5.04	0.89	5.00	0.87
Improvisation	5.44	0.73	4.34	1.03
Structuring	5.24	0.78	4.76	0.92
Adaptation and control	5.24	0.73	4.78	0.83
Optimizing processes	4.57	1.09	5.15	0.82
Communication	5.38	0.90	5.17	0.84
Assertiveness	5.34	0.85	4.65	1.01
Conflict competence	4.57	1.15	5.45	0.72
Team cooperation	5.11	0.93	5.22	0.77
Public sensitivity	4.97	0.89	4.87	0.99
Team sensitivity and care	4.71	1.12	5.34	0.82
Empathy	4.45	1.11	5.20	0.86
Development	4.80	1.08	5.23	0.77
Role clarity and personal integrity	5.31	0.81	5.06	0.94
Reflection competence	5.08	0.93	5.30	0.75
Resilience	5.42	0.75	4.79	0.92
Self-regulation	5.48	0.70	4.74	0.93
Willingness and ability to learn	4.89	1.08	5.28	0.76

Note. Competencies were rated from 1 = *not important at all* to 6 = *very important* for within and between action phases. N = 601.

6) Summary of exploratory analyses

We calculated two exploratory analyses in our study. First, we calculated Kruskal-Wallis tests for potential differences between the leadership ranks of participants (i.e., group vs. platoon vs. higher-ranked leaders) regarding their importance ratings. We did not find any significant differences in this analysis. Second, we calculated additional Kruskal-Wallis tests for potential differences between the type of engagement (voluntary fire services vs. career fire services vs. both) and importance ratings. We found significant relations with small effect sizes ($r = [.13;.20]$), yet they did not add up to a distinguishable systematic pattern.

In action phases: We found significant relations for “adaptation and control”, $X^2(2, N = 601) = 8.4, p < .05$, “conflict competence”, $X^2(2, N = 601) = 10.91, p < .01$, and “willingness and ability to learn”, $X^2(2, N = 601) = 7.36, p < .05$. Post hoc analyses were calculated by Dunn’s tests revealed that firefighters who work exclusively for a career fire service ($M = 5.45, SD = 0.64$) rate “adaptation and control” as significantly more important compared to those, who work for both career and voluntary fire services ($M = 5.17, SD = 0.76$). For “conflict competence”, participants who work exclusively in voluntary fire services ($M = 4.73, SD = 1.11$) indicated a significantly higher importance rating than participants who work in both ($M = 4.43, SD = 1.14$). For “willingness and ability to learn”, participants who work exclusively in career fire services ($M = 5.17, SD = 1.11$) indicated a significantly higher importance rating than participants who work exclusively in voluntary fire services ($M = 4.84, SD = 1.06$) and those who work in both ($M = 4.86, SD = 1.08$).

Regarding importance ratings *in interim phases*, we found significant differences for the competencies “adaptation and control”, $X^2(2, N = 601) = 8.21, p < .05$, “communication”, $X^2(2, N = 601) = 8.18, p < .05$, “public sensitivity”, $X^2(2, N = 601) = 15.42, p < .001$, and “willingness and ability to learn”, $X^2(2, N = 601) = 12.08, p < .01$. For *interim phases*, post hoc tests indicated that firefighters working in career fire services ($M = 5.06, SD = 0.71$) rated “adaptation and control” significantly as more important compared to both those who work exclusively in voluntary fire services ($M = 4.47, SD = 1.11$) and those who work voluntarily and vocationally in fire services ($M = 4.76, SD = 0.86$). For “communication,” participants who work in both voluntary and career fire services ($M = 5.28, SD = 0.80$) rated the competence as significantly more important compared to those who exclusively work in voluntary fire services ($M = 5.08, SD = 1.11$). For “public sensitivity,” participants who work exclusively in voluntary fire services ($M = 5.03, SD = 1.11$) rated the competence as significantly more important compared to both those who work exclusively in career fire services ($M = 4.69, SD = 0.87$) and those who work in both ($M = 4.71, SD = 1.08$). For “willingness and ability to learn,” participants who work exclusively in career fire services ($M = 5.56, SD = 0.69$) indicated a significantly higher importance compared to both those who work exclusively in voluntary fire services ($M = 5.28, SD = 1.11$) and those who work in both ($M = 5.21, SD = 0.80$).

7) Table 4: Standard deviations of future competency importance ratings

Competence	Mean	SD
Firefighting expertise	4.92	1.30
Analytical competence	5.09	1.07
Decision-making	5.10	1.20
Planning and organizing	5.31	1.14
Improvisation	5.31	1.23
Structuring	5.09	1.04
Adaptation and control	5.01	1.09
Optimizing processes	5.21	1.23
Communication	5.83	1.17
Assertiveness	5.14	1.26
Conflict competence	5.66	1.14
Team cooperation	5.67	1.18
Public sensitivity	5.25	1.24
Team sensitivity and care	5.69	1.14
Empathy	5.35	1.20
Development	5.23	1.12
Role clarity and personal integrity	4.94	1.18
Reflection competence	5.06	1.17
Resilience	5.08	1.19
Self-regulation	4.86	1.05
Willingness and ability to learn	5.34	1.18

Note. Development of importance was answered on a scale from 1 (= *much less important*), over 4 (= *equally important*), to 7 (= *much more important*). N = 601.